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GEO-STUDIES FORUM

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THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC DETERMINANT OF ACCESS TO INFORMAL DOMESTIC WATER SUPPLY IN IJEBU-ODE, OGUN STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: Potable water is becoming a scarce commodity in many regions of the world due to climate change and increasing demand. The aim of this paper is to examine the inequality in access to potable water in the informal water market among urban residents within the Ijebu-Ode city of Nigeria. The objectives are to identify the socio-economic factors determining access to potable water, highlight factors shaping residents' access to equitable and sustainable water supply within the city. This paper which was derived from a survey used a mixed-method design with cluster sampling procedure for selection of residential quarters. Five hundred and seven households were randomly selected for study using Cochran's sample size formula. Descriptive statistics was used to analyse major sources of potable water, multiple linear regression model was used to analyse socio-economic factors determining resident's access to informal water supply. Findings revealed that 73.6% of respondents use hand pump borehole, water seller/kiosk (7.0%), public tap (6.2%), package sachet water (4.7%), and 3.8% of respondents use unimproved water supply. Regression model analysis indicate a positive relationship between access to water and variables such as occupation of household Head (HHH) (Beta = .075, $p = 0.131$), age of HHH (Beta = .025, $p = 0.642$), average monthly income (Beta = 0.087, $p = 0.093$), and storage facility (Beta = 0.099, $p = 0.044$). The paper recommends establishment of water services regulatory body, provision of loans for informal water market operators and promotion of informal water market to boost access to potable water in the cities.

Keywords: Potable Water, Informal Market, Accessibility, Socio-infrastructure, Urban Residents.

INTRODUCTION

Freshwater is limited in many regions due to climate change and increasing water demand (Onafeso, 2020). However, development ideologies have framed water as a socioeconomic good within public policy (Rogers et al., 1998). While access to water varies widely across different regions of the world and periods, its availability, distribution, and accessibility are influenced by a complex interplay of natural and anthropological factors, together with cultural, institutional, economic, and social elements (Du Plessis, 2017). These factors continuously shape the dynamics of water

allocation, determining who receives what quantity of water, where, and for what purposes.

In Nigeria, the responsibility for water supply services and delivery rests with the state governments, while the federal government through the Federal Ministry of Water Resources (FMWR) performs oversight functions and is also responsible for national water sanitation and health policies, directives, rules, and plans. However, most water facilities have not functioned for a long time as they break easily and often fall into disrepair. The continuous failure of water,

sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) infrastructures in providing access to water for households and poor level of services by public water service providers has led to seeking for an alternate source of water supply on the side of the household (Luis et al. 2018). Within Nigeria setting, the policy design has not successfully enhanced access to water services, as urban areas have experienced a huge reduction in access to improved water services, at the rate of about 80 % to 67 % within 1990 and 2004 Acey (2007). Studies have shown that about six out of every ten Nigerians lack access to safe water for domestic usage (Agada, 2020; Obeta, 2019; Ezenwaji, et al. 2016), trend in access to water shows a decline in the number of people with access to water to be 11%, 9% and 10% for the year 2018, 2019 and 2021 respectively, similarly World Bank report on access to water in Nigeria indicates an estimates of 2.31 million water points in Nigeria three quarter (75%) are self-supplied out of which 43% are boreholes, (Federal Ministry of Water Resources , 2021).

Other reports indicated that accessibility to potable water in Nigeria's urban centres has taken a downward trend within the last thirty years, studies show a decline of 25% between 1990 and 2015 (that is between 32% to 7% between 1990 and 2015, World Bank, (2017). Similarly, in Ogun state, access to basic water supply, sanitation and hygiene services slump by 25% from 12% in 2018 to 9% in 2021, so also is a decline 25% in basic water supply and hygiene from 12% to 9% during the same period, (Federal Ministry of Water Resources, WASHNORM Report, 2021).

Consequentially, millions depend on non-state water suppliers such as the informal for-profit water vendors, which are individuals of small enterprises that produce, and dispense or sell water to households at grassroots levels in towns and rural areas, if not for their efforts many urban dwellers will have no access to

water services (Agada, 2020; Obeta, 2019; Ezenwaji, et al. 2016; Adeleye, et al. 2014).

The informal water market includes unorganized retailers selling water to households, outside the government-organized channelled network structure. This group are not subject to any of government monitoring structures, or ecological or quality codes, members may include stationary private borehole owners, mobile cart pushers, water kiosk etc. (Allouche, 2011; UN Habitat, 2010; Kjellén and McGranahan, 2006, 2009).

This occurrence could be attributed to a rapid increase in population growth and unrestrained urbanization, poor resource allocation, combined with poor organizational ability and corruption, as part of the multifaceted difficulty facing adequate potable water supply in Nigeria, and only about half of the population have main access to safe water (WHO/UNICEF Joint Monitoring Programme report, 2023, 2015; Ishaku, et al. 2010; Emoabino and Alayande 2007; Montgomery and Elimelech, 2007). The human right to water, established as international law in 2010, through United Nations Resolution, as adopted and incorporated in Nigeria's national laws, is to "guarantee worldwide safe, clean, accessible, and affordable drinking water" (United Nations Resolution, 64/292, 2010). But regardless of the adoption of the United Nations Resolutions on the human right to water, Nigeria like most developing nations, where the right to water is recognized, still experiences practical difficulties in extending this right to all its citizens (Miroso and Harris, 2012).

The accessibility to water in quantity and quality is severely affected by human-induced activities. For example, water demand has increased as an outcome of rapid population growth and other demographic changes, with

changes in consumption patterns. The supply and distribution are in decline due to institutional inefficiencies and infrastructural decay. It is therefore pertinent to understand how the residents who lack access to potable water meet their requirements for water need. The objectives of the study are to examine the source of water used by residents, and as well to determining the socio-economic factors determining access to potable water within the study area. Therefore, this study is thus aimed at highlighting the factors that determine residents' access to equitable and sustainable water supply in Ijebu-Ode, Ogun State, Nigeria.

While many emerging cities possess similar characteristics of reliance on informal sector activities in the provision of utility services in meeting the water demand and access of their residents, this study can provide a better understanding of the relationship existing within the activities between the urban population and the importance of the roles played by the informal water market (IWM), in the direction of providing access to water and it will also assist in policy formulation.

STUDY AREA

Ijebu-Ode a major urban centre located in the interior of the South-Western Nigeria. Absolutely, the study area, figure 1, (lies within Latitude $6,79313^0$ to 6.85921^0 North and Longitude 3.89947^0 and 3.95116^0 East). It serves as second order city in Ogun State after Abeokuta, with an area of about 192 kilometres square, (Encyclopædia Britannica Inc., 2012). Due to uncontrolled urbanization, and non-stop physical expansion it has practically merged with nearby settlements. (Mabogunje and Roberts, 2004)

Ijebu-Ode experiences the warm tropical climate has a mean annual rainfall of between

1523 mm and 2340 mm and averages daily temperature at about 28^0 C. Rainfall is generally heavy, having two regime called "Double Maxima" April-July by way of short break in August, recognized as "August break" and the second regime starts in September-October however the rainfall reaches its peak in both July and September. Humidity is usually high, with significant drop during the Harmattan season, from mid-November till early January. Annual relative humidity is about 81%, (Bakare et al. 2015)

The city is located in the interior of tropical lowland rain forest region. The most important flora cover is made up of multiplicity of species arranged in a straight down forest structure with a nascent layer of large trees of about 60 meters high comprising trees like, *Khaya entandrophragma*, *Triplochiton*, *Terminalia*, *Chlorophora*, *Lovoa trichilioides*, *Lophira alata*. Topographically, it is an area of gentle rolling plain of about 100 metre above the sea level. The city geology is of basement complex rock mainly of old rigid crystalline rock of igneous and metamorphic origin, (Oke and Oyebola, (2012), Mabogunje and Roberts, (2004). The population of Ijebu-Ode is on the rise speedily, mainly due to many factors such as, immigration and rural-urban migration. Due to rural-urban economic interactions and a portion of the population living within the outer fringes of the urban area.

By 2006, the city has a population estimate of 157,161 (Nation Bureau of Statistics NBS, 2006). Due to migration, Ijebu-Ode is rapidly growing with widely dispersed sub-urban region, with a projected population of 368,749 at a population growth rate of 3.36%. The population density is about 1224 person/km², (World Population Review, 2022).

Figure 1: Map of the study area.

Source: Author 2025

MATERIALS AND METHODS RESEARCH DESIGN

The study adopted a quantitative approach combined with a mixed-method design for arriving at a scientific and more reliable data collection process. Using non-experimental approach in data collection phase, data were collected through questionnaire survey method and, on the field observation. Prior to the field survey, research questions were identified and well related to the study objective of the study. The statement of hypothesis “There is no significant relationship between the socioeconomic characteristics of household and access to informal sources of domestic water supply” was built to prove the significance of the result, in addition, a criterion p-value for evaluating statistical significance of the results, was set to be either 0.05 and test the hypothesis using a null hypothesis

significance testing (NHST) based on observations of samples.

TYPES AND SOURCES OF DATA

Data Requirements for the Study include both primary and secondary data, the primary data required for the study were obtained through direct field observation and personal interview through the use of questionnaire as instrument of data collection. While the secondary data include the population figure and map of the study area obtained from public repository. The validation of the question items followed the three stages necessary for quality assurance, face validity was compared with multiple household survey questionnaire samples to remove ambiguity to ensure relativity to research questions, followed by content validity all construct examined by expert for clear definition, in addition, pilot survey was

carried out with a sample size of 90 questionnaire distributed across the nine cluster within the study area to test the practicability of obtaining data using the instrument of data collection and to correct any arising problems. These questions items cover the socio-economic characteristics of the population, factors affecting water availability and supply, coping strategies, perception on willingness to pay for water and factors affecting ability to pay for water.

SAMPLING DESIGN

Cluster sampling, a type of probability sampling technique was implemented for this study in order to create a sample frame, as it allows for the selection of elements of the population randomly in a logically occurring or previously existing grouping, such as a geographical or physical collections. This is the case since there was no up-to-date list of individuals or households, but only the maps of the area. The target population figure is 368,749 for year 2022 projection, while the sampling frame is the nine (9) areas (clusters), based on the pattern after Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) Directory 2015 for polling units located within the geographical metropolitan area of Ijebu-Ode all put together to form a single area frame. The frame was then thoroughly assessed to determine under, over, or multiple coverages necessary for adjustments. Next is the division of the sample population list (N) with the total number of clusters to determine number of samples for each cluster. This was followed by simple random sampling without replacement to select participant as this means that selecting one member of the population is independent of others, this technique was based on the premise the population is highly homogenous, (Cochran 1977; Statistics Canada, 2010). To select the desire sample size, lottery method in which numbers assign to residential buildings on streets basis were

written on paper chips, thoroughly mixed together in a container, the numbered chips were then picked by the research assistants to obtain the elements within each cluster until the whole sample size is arrive at (Singh, 2003).

The Cochran’s formula for calculating the sample size, (Barlet et al, 2001; Statistics Canada 2010; Cochran, 1977) was used to derive the sample size.

Required sample size (n_0):

$$n_0 = \frac{(t)^2 * (p)(q)}{(d)^2} \quad (\text{eq 1})$$

Where:

t = value for selected alpha level of .025 in each tail = 1.96. (The alpha level of .05 indicates the level of risk the researcher is willing to take that true margin of error may exceed the acceptable margin of error)

(p)(q) = estimate of variance = .25 (maximum possible proportion (.5) * 1- maximum possible proportion (.5) produces maximum possible sample size

d = acceptable margin of error for proportion being estimated = .05 (error researcher is willing to except).

Finally, five hundred and seven (507) households were randomly chosen for the administration of questionnaire, the survey was based on field observation. Observation approach on the field was longitudinal in nature because the observations were performed at different points in time. A total of 507 copies of questionnaire were administered in the study area, 102 were rejected and not included in the analysis due to incomplete answers or multiple responses. Therefore, 405 accurately completed copies of questionnaire were used for the analysis.

METHODS OF DATA ANALYSIS

The analytical technique used include both descriptive and inferential statistics, central

tendency was used to identify the sources of water used by residents and measure of dispersion, Multiple Regression Analysis and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was carried out to investigate which factor(s) determines access to domestic water supply. All analysis was carried out using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 20.0.

The category of the variables include, Dependent Variables (DV); Access to water and Independent Variable (IV); Gender of Respondent, Age of household Head, Water Storage capacity, Number of Dependant, Marital status of household head, Occupation of House hold Head, Education level of household head, Rented/Owned Building, Average Monthly Income, Number of households in a building, Number of households in a building, Length of stay in a building, Group that fetch water, Average cost of water and Quantity of water purchased in litres.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section discussed the result of findings of socio-economic factors determining residents' access to informal domestic water supply in Ijebu-ode metropolis.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

Table 1, shows the result of the descriptive statistic undertaken to elucidate the central tendency analyses for all the socio-economic variables. The analyses were conducted on a robust sample size of 405 respondent and listwise deletion was applied to address the issues of missing data. Marital status has a mean value of 2.28 and standard deviation of 0.70 ($M = 2.28$, $SD = 0.70$), skewness was determined to be 2.40 indicating slight positive skew, while kurtosis was 4.79 signifying a peaked distribution. Similarly

mean value for educational level was, 3.67 with a standard deviation of 1.15, ($M = 3.67$, $SD = 1.15$), skewness was established to be -0.99 this display a negative skew while kurtosis was 0.07 indicating a slightly peaked distribution. Furthermore, the mean value for occupation was 4.96 with a standard deviation of 2.09 ($M = 4.96$, $SD = 2.09$), skewness was established to be 0.78 and a kurtosis of -0.11 , implying a right-side distribution with a short-left tail. Also, the mean value for income stood at 2.50, with a standard deviation of 1.94 ($M = 2.50$, $SD = 1.94$), skewness remains at 2.44 and kurtosis indicate 7.0, this gives a moderate positive and peaked distribution.

The mean value for number of dependents was 4.36 alongside a standard deviation to be 2.59, skewness remains 15.38 indicating a high positive skew, while kurtosis was 284.49 suggesting a heavily peaked distribution. Furthermore, the mean value for number of dependent in training was 2.90 with standard deviation to be 1.17 ($M = 2.90$, $SD = 1.17$), while skewness was established to be 0.32, the kurtosis stood at -53 , this indicates a moderate deeply flat distribution. the mean value for types of building stood at 2.13 together with a standard deviation of 0.73 ($M = 2.13$, $SD = 0.73$), skewness was -0.20 indicating a slightly negative distribution while the kurtosis was determined to be -1.08 implying a flat a distribution with relative flatness.

Likewise, the mean value for building ownership was 1.40 with standard deviation of 0.51, ($M = 1.40$, $SD = 0.51$) skewness was determine to be 0.63 indicating slightly positive skew while kurtosis was -1.08 , indicating a distribution with relative flatness. Equally, mean value for number of HH in a building was 3.71 with a standard deviation of 2.45 ($M = 3.71$, $SD = 2.45$) skewness remain at 1.03 showing a moderate skew while kurtosis was 1.54 indicating slightly peaked distribution. Additionally, mean value for length of stay is determine to be 2.08 with a

standard deviation of 1.17 (M= 2.08, Sd= 1.17), skewness is established as 0.62 implying a slender skew while kurtosis stood at – 1.14 indicating a distribution with relative flatness. Finally, the mean value for storage

facilities was 4.02 with a standard deviation of 1.44 (M = 4.02, SD = 1.44) skewness was determine to be – 0.07, indicating an insignificant skew, while kurtosis stood at – 0.59 signifying a distribution with a highly relative flatness.

Table 1: Summary of Central Tendency for the socio-economic factors determining resident’s access to informal domestic water supply.

	Valid	Missing	Mean	Standard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Marital Status	405	0	2.28	0.07	2.40	4.79
Education Level	405	0	3.67	1.16	-0.99	0.07
Occupation	405	0	4.96	2.09	0.78	-0.11
Income	405	0	2.50	1.94	2.44	7.00
No of Dependent	405	0	4.36	2.59	15.38	284.49
No of Dependent in Training	405	0	2.90	1.17	0.32	-0.53
Types Of Building	405	0	2.13	0.73	-0.20	-1.08
Building ownership	405	0	1.40	0.51	0.63	-1.08
No of HH in a Building	405	0	3.71	2.45	1.03	1.54
Length of stay	405	0	2.08	1.17	0.62	-1.14
Storage Facility	405	0	4.02	1.44	-0.07	-0.59

Source: Authors’ Fieldwork, 2025

HOUSEHOLDS’ MAJOR SOURCES OF WATER FOR DRINKING

In Table 2, show the analysis of the frequency count on household major source of drinking water. Majority of the respondents (73.6%) indicated that hand pump borehole serves as main source of drinking water, following this (7.9%) respondent stated that water seller/kiosk is their main source of drinking water, likewise, (4.7%) of the respondents reported packaged water as main source of drinking water. Equally, (6.2%) of the respondents reported public tap/ standalone pipe as major source of drinking water. While

few of the respondents (3.0%) signifies that pipe connection to house as major source of drinking water. Furthermore, only some (2.7%) of the respondent identified unprotected hand dug well as the main source of drinking water. Further examination showed that not many (0.7%) of the respondent disclosed protected spring as main source of drinking water, while a small amount of the respondents (0.5%) signifies tanker trucks as main source of drinking water. Finally, very few of the respondents (0.3%) identified unprotected spring and rain water collection each as the main source of water.

Table 2: Households’ Major sources of Water for Drinking

Household major sources of water for drinking	Frequency	Percent
Public tap/Standpipe	25	6.2
Handpumps/Boreholes	298	73.6
Water seller/Kiosk	32	7.9
Piped connection to house	12	2.9
Protected Spring	3	0.7
Packaged water (Bottled or Sachets)	19	4.7
Tanker trucks	2	0.5
Unprotected hand-dug well	11	2.7
Surface water (lake, pond, dam and river)	1	0.3
Unprotected spring	1	0.3
Rain water collection	1	0.3
Total	405	100

Source: Authors’ Fieldwork, 2025

FACTORS DETERMINING RESIDENTS’ ACCESS TO INFORMAL DOMESTIC WATER SUPPLY

The regression coefficients presented in Table 3, provide insights into the relationships between various independent variables, (Average cost of water, Educational Level, No of Household in a building, Water Storage Facility, No of Dependant, Rented/Owned Building, Group that fetch Water, Marital Status, Occupation of HH, Gender of Respondent, Length of stay in the building, Average Monthly Income, Age of household head) and the dependent variable, which is "Access to Regular water supply in dry and wet season." Starting with the intercept (constant), the coefficient of 1.147 ($p = 0.000$) indicates the expected value of the dependent variable when all other predictor variables are zero. This intercept is statistically significant, suggesting a baseline level of access to water supply in the absence of other factors.

Examining the standardized coefficients (Beta), it was observed that several variables show significant relationships with access to

water supply. Marital status has a notable negative impact (Beta = -0.164, $p = 0.001$), indicating that being married is associated with lower access compared to other marital. The number of dependents also has a negative influence (Beta = -0.100, $p = 0.041$), in relation to the two factors a hint is that more dependents in a household may linked to reduced access to water in cases where purchasing power is very low due to other competing household needs.

Additionally, the quantity of water purchased in liters (Quantity of water purchased in liters) shows a significant negative relationship (Beta = -0.160, $p = 0.002$), suggesting that households purchasing smaller amount of water tend to have less access to domestic water supply, other variables showing a negative relationship indicating less access to water include like, Average cost of water (Beta = -0.11, $p=0.819$), Quantities of water purchased in liters (Beta = -.160, $p = 0.002$), group that fetch water (Beta = - .008, $p = 0.879$), Marital status (Beta = -.164, $p = 0.001$), Educational level (Beta = -.046, $p = 0.370$), Rented/Owned Building (Beta = -.025, $p =$

0.625), No of Household in a building (Beta = -.096, p = 0.051), Length of stay in the building (Beta = -.021, p = 0.694), all these variables indicate an inverse relationship indicating that an increase in the unit of anyone of them will show a decrease in access.

Conversely, variables like, Occupation of H/hold Head (Beta = .075, p = 0.131), Age of household head (Beta = .025, p = 0.642) Average Monthly Income (Beta = 0.087, p = 0.093) and Water Storage Facility (Beta = 0.099, p = 0.044) show positive relationships, indicating that occupation of H/hold Head,

age of H/hold Head higher income and better to storage facilities are associated with improved water access, while only storage facilities showed a significant p-value. From the above discourse, coefficients provide valuable information for understanding the impact of various socio-economic factors on access to water supply, highlighting specific variables that show a relationship in influencing access to water within the studied population.

In the context of the hypothesis where the null statement posits no significant relationship between socio-economic characteristics of household and access to informal source of domestic water supply

Table 3: Regression Coefficients Table showing relationships between various independent variables and the dependent variable.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized t Coefficients	Sig.
	B	Std. Error		
(Constant)	1.147	.195	5.886	0.000
Gender of Respondent	-.044	.042	-.053	0.295
Age of household head	.001	.002	.025	0.642
Marital Status	-.100	.031	-.164	0.001
Educational Level	-.016	.018	-.046	0.370
Occupation of H/hold Head	.015	.010	.075	0.131
Average Monthly Income	.028	.017	.087	0.093
Number of Dependand	-.016	.008	-.100	0.041
Rented/Owned Building	-.020	.040	-.025	0.625
Number of Household in a building	-.016	.008	-.096	0.051
Length of stay in the building	-.007	.018	-.021	0.694
Group that fetches Water	-.002	.012	-.008	0.879
Water Storage Facility	.028	.014	.099	0.044
Average cost of water	-.006	.028	-.011	0.819
Quantity of water purchased in litres	-.048	.015	-.160	0.002

a. Dependent Variable: Access to domestic water supply in dry and wet season

Source: Authors' Fieldwork, 2025

The regression model Table 3, suggests a weak relationship between socio-economic characteristics of households and access to

domestic water supply. The R-square value of 0.081 indicates that only about 8.1% of the variability in water supply access can be

explained by the predictor variables in the model, suggesting limited predictive power. The implication based on the result of the

analyses suggest that more studies is needed in this area in order to ascertain the level of predictive power of the independent (predictor) variables.

Table 4: Regression Model of socio-economic characteristics of households and access to domestic water supply.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate
1	0.285 ^a	0.081	0.051	0.399

Source: Authors' Fieldwork, 2025

- a. **Predictors:** (Constant), Average cost of water, Educational Level, No of Household in a building, Water Storage Facility, No of Dependant, Rented/Owned Building, Group that fetch Water, Marital Status, Occupation of HH, Gender of Respondent, Length of stay in the building, Average Monthly Income, Age of household head.

The ANOVA results presented in Table 4, indicate the overall significance of the regression model. The regression sum of squares (SS) is 5.501 with 13 degrees of freedom (df), resulting in a mean square (MS) of 0.423. This means that the variation explained by the regression model is significantly larger than what would be expected by chance alone. The

residual sum of squares is 62.237 with 391 degrees of freedom, resulting in a smaller mean square of 0.159, indicating the unexplained variance within the model. The table shows an F of 2.658 which yielded a p-value of 0.001, suggesting that the model explains a significant amount of variance in the dependent variable compared to the residual variance. Therefore, we accept null hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant relationship between Socio-Economic characteristics of Households and access to Domestic Water Supply. In summary, these results suggest that the regression model is a statistically valid and significant predictor of the dependent variable.

Table 5: ANOVA Model indicating relationship between Socio-Economic characteristics of Households and access to Domestic Water Supply

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	5.501	13	0.423	2.658	0.001 ^b
Residual	62.237	391	0.159		
Total	67.738	404			

Source: Authors' Fieldwork, 2025

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The regression coefficients provide an insight into the relationships between various independent variables and the dependent variable, which is "Access to Regular water

supply in dry and wet season." Starting with the intercept (constant), the coefficient of 1.147 in Table 3, (p = 0.000) indicates the expected value of the dependent variable when all other predictor variables are zero.

This intercept is statistically significant, suggesting a baseline level of access to water supply in the absence of other factors.

Examining the standardized coefficients (Beta), it was observed that several variables show significant relationships with access to water supply. Marital status has a notable negative impact (Beta = -0.164, $p = 0.001$), indicating that being married is associated with lower access compared to other marital statuses, this is contrary to earlier study (Gurung et al. 2023), reported marital status as a statistically significant predictors of determinants of access.

The number of dependents also has a negative influence implying that more dependents in a household are linked to reduced access to water, this implies that a larger household has low access to water which may be related to the amount purchased versus quantity needed by the household. This is supported by the study of (Simelane et al. 2020), who reported in their study, on the determinants of households' access to improved drinking water sources, that higher number of household members was negatively associated with access to improved drinking water sources when likened to household with fewer members.

Average cost of water also has negative impact on access to water, a fact supported by (Ohwo and Abotutu, 2014), in a study of households' access to potable water supply in Yenengoa, who stated that despite high presence of boreholes within short distances to homes, residents only acquire one fifth of quantity of water needed, indicating low access to domestic water, as caused by the high cost of water supply which in addition affect the quantity of water purchased in liters which also contribute to less access. Additionally, the quantity of water purchased in liters (Quantity of water purchased in liters)

shows a significant negative relationship, suggesting that households purchasing

smaller quantities of water tend to have less access to domestic water supply.

Contrariwise, average monthly income affects access positively, this is in line with findings by (Abualtayef et al. (2019), Makwinja et al. (2019), Nkoana et al. (2019) Aslam et al. (2018), who similarly found a statistically significant relationship between income and access to water and payments. Age of household head, shows significant relationship with access to water which correspond with the study of (Abdu et al. (2016), that recognised that age, have positive influence on access to safe drinking water. In contrast to this argument is the study of (Omondi and Jackson (2022), who stated that the marginal effects of age does not have a significant relationship with water source, thus age of household head does not affect access to water.

In addition, the study reveals a significant relationship between the occupation of household head and access to water. This conformed with the study of (Koskei et al. (2013), and (Briand and Laré (2010) who described that occupation of household head have both negative and significant relationship with water source use. Contrarily (Arouna and Dabbert (2010), reported a negative relationship between household occupation and access to water source. Water Storage Facility show positive relationships, indicating that higher income and access to storage facilities are associated with better water access, this assertion is also in line with the findings of (Oyerinde and Jacob (2021).

These coefficients provide valuable information for understanding the impact of various socio-economic factors on access to water supply, highlighting specific variables

that significantly influence this access within the studied population.

CONCLUSION

The paper identified socio-economic factors determining residents access to informal domestic water supply and found married status has a notable negative impact, indicating that being married is associated with lower access compared to other marital statuses. The number of dependents also has a negative influence, implying that more dependents in a household are linked to demand access to potable water. Additionally, the quantity of water purchased shows a significant negative relationship, suggesting that households purchasing smaller amount of water tend to have less access to domestic water supply. Conversely, variables like, occupation of the household head, age, average monthly income and water storage facility showed positive relationships. Meaning that higher income and access to storage facilities are associated with better water access.

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RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this paper, recommendations are as follows;

1. The paper recommends establishment of water services regulatory body, to be responsible for monitoring, control and policy guideline formulation for proper organization of the market as well to protect residents from exploitation.
2. There should be provision and subsidy opportunity for the informal water market operators, this will reduce the burden of sourcing capital for initial start-up operational cost, and also reduce the effect of market forces affecting production.
3. The promotion of informal water market to boost access to potable water in the cities, through public-private partnership collaboration in providing water to the less privileged areas that would have been denied access to water as public institution inefficiencies

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